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Demographic Factors Moderating the Influence of Career Growth on Unethical Behaviour among Personnel of Nigerian Customs Service

Akeem A. Kenku Ph.D

Department of Psychology,
Nasarawa State University, Keffi, Nigeria.
Email: akeemkenku@yahoo.com

Ajibola A. Ishola

Department of Psychology,
University of Ibadan, Ibadan, Nigeria.
Email: ajibola_ishola@yahoo.co.uk

Abstract

This study examines moderating influence of socio-demographic characteristics on the associations among career related factors and unethical behaviour among personnel in the Nigerian Customs Service (NCS). The study was a cross sectional research design. The demographic characteristics revealed that 38.13 (S.D = 3.47). 64.4% of the respondents were males while 35.6% were females. Two hundred and Fifty (250) officers were purposively selected from the units under the Zone C of the Nigeria Customs service (NCS) in Edo/Delta state Nigeria. The participants responded to a questionnaire containing Career growth scale, Work Salience Questionnaire (WSQ) and Career Salience Questionnaire (CSQ), Work Deviance Behaviour Scale (WDBS) and demographic profile. The collected data was analyzed using Pearson correlation, moderated hierarchical multiple regression analysis at $p \leq 0.05$ level of significance. Results revealed that career growth had an inverse association with unethical work behaviour ($r = -.43, p < .001$); while positive associations was observed among career salience ($r = .24, p < .001$), gender ($r_{pb} = .28, p < .001$), years of experience ($r = .25, p < .001$) and unethical work behaviour. Age and sex moderated the influence of career growth in predicting unethical behaviour among NCS personnel. ($F_{(8, 252)} = 28.17, p = .003, R^2 = 0.48, \Delta R^2 = 0.06$). The addition of the interaction terms (Career growth x Sex ($\beta = -.27, p < .01$; Career growth x Age ($\beta = -.22, p < .01$) yielded a significant 6% increase in model fit ($\Delta R^2 = .06, \Delta F_{(1,242)} = 9.34, p = .003$) and the interaction terms were significant. This study thus concluded that gender and age shaped the influence of poor career growth on consequential involvement in unethical work practice among customs officers. It was advised that career motivation programme should be offered to serving customs officers.

Key words: career growth, career salience, unethical behaviour

Introduction

The Nigeria Customs Service (NCS) is one important government paramilitary institution which plays an important role in the Nigerian economy and stability. This institution currently has been identified to be going through daunting challenges which range from leadership problems, low moral and increasing levels of unethical practices within its rank and file (Premium Times, 2017). A major albatross is the adverse effects of indiscipline on the staff performance and organizational effectiveness. Unethical behaviour of lack of discipline and involvement in corrupt practices have been identified to have caused a greater damage to the performance of the Customs services leading to loss humungous amount of revenue to the country, loss of live (Personnel and civilians), and general distrust against the Nigerian Customs service among the general populace. One key way of reducing this behaviour is identifying key organizational or individual factors promoting these untoward behaviours. Several factors identified include; nepotism, leadership styles, training, motivation and individual characteristics. Among the plethora of factors, Kenku and Adedayo (2019) have identified that career related factor is a major factor exacerbating these problems among the NCS rank and file.

Career progress and stability have been identified to very important to a workforce since it offers long-term success, increased salary, job stability and job happiness (Dialoke, Adighije & Nkechi, 2017). Organisation dedication to progress in employee career will enable a better motivated staff and a more effective organisation to be achieved (Dialoke et al., 2017). However, contrary to expectation Kenku and Adedayo (2019) identified that many customs personnel with long years of experience were not adequately compensated due to career stagnation and lack of promotion considering their job input. The stagnation thus affected the level of remunerations, training and other benefit they could have received subsequently fueling increasing disposition to engage in unethical practices. Whereas the issues of remuneration were often attended to, problem of lack of promotion or slow career growth and poor career management is a major debacle (Kenku & Adedayo, 2019). Prior study has established that organizational career growth has been shown to have positive effects on job related attitude (Weng et al., 2011), and a local study has confirmed that career growth and salience influenced unethical behaviour (Kenku & Adedayo, 2019).

Despite these, a gap identified is the possible moderating role of socio-demographic characteristics in career related factor and unethical practices relationships have not been explored in extant literature and in Nigeria to be specific (Dialoke et al., 2017; Kenku & Adedayo, 2019). This is supported by the view of Lehnert et al. (2015) who observed that the role of socio-demographic variables in research on organizational ethical behaviour is very important. Lehnert et al. (2015) pointed out that an emphasis on interaction is needed to really grasp ethical behavioural boundary conditions. They allude that complex relationships between psychological variables and social factors give great opportunities to better understand the interaction between demographics which often dampen organizational interventions geared towards reducing unethical practices in organisations (Brienza & Bobocel, 2017; Khoreva & Tenhiälä, 2016). Thus, this study explored the fact that the relationship between career growth and unethical behaviour may not be a smooth sail as underlining socio-demographic factors may have shaped the employee's reaction to lack of career growth and involvement in unethical behaviour. Based on these, this study assesses the potential role of age, gender and years of experience in Nigerian Customs Service personnel involvement in unethical behaviour.

The Socioemotional selectivity theory (SST; Carstensen, 1992) provides a converging evidence that age moderates employees' job-related attitude as they grow older. The theory

proposed that as people age, they increasingly prioritize positive social emotion and down-regulate negative social emotion, and they become more agreeable and less neurotic. Similarly, with age, individuals become more empathetic, show improvements in reasoning about social dilemmas, and engage less in antisocial behaviour. These position was supported by empirical evidence which demonstrated that employee age is associated with increased motivation toward positive workplace relationships, greater cooperation and respect, increased orientation toward generative identity, and decreased motivation toward achievement, status, instrumental control, and competition in the workplace (Kooij et al., 2011; Stamov-Roßnagel & Biemann, 2012; Tenhiälä et al., 2013). Consistent with these findings, research has revealed negative relations between employee age and antisocial tendencies such as deviance, and related constructs such as revenge and retaliation (Bobocel, 2013). Therefore, employee age might alter the personal relevance of workplace experiences that are associated with fulfilling instrumental and relational needs. Looking at lack of career growth, no research has integrated the literatures on aging and reaction to lack of promotion whether age may induce involvement in unethical work behaviour or reduce its.

The second moderator is gender; reactions to injustice may not be homogenous across different employee groups, such as women and men. The majority of studies predict that male and female employees react differently to organisational injustice. Empirical research has demonstrated that female employees often react less strongly to pay inequity than male employees (Khoreva & Tenhiälä, 2016). In contrast, female employees have been found to react more strongly to procedural justice than their male counterparts (Clay-Warner, Culatta & James, 2013; Khoreva & Tenhiälä, 2016). Recent evidence suggests that females react more to procedural(un)fairness than men, even if they do not always show it via expressed or noticed behavioural differences (Dulebohn et al., 2016). The majority of previous studies have suggested that women place greater value on the fairness of workplace procedures than men, while men value financial rewards more than women. Nevertheless, we do not fully understand how female employees will react in terms of deviant or unethical behaviour when they experience lack of career growth. specifically; the objectives of the study are as follows:

- To investigate contribution of career growth and career salience to unethical behaviour
- To investigate moderating influence of age, gender and experience to customs officers' unethical behaviour

Hypotheses

1. Career salience, career growth and socio-demographic variables would significantly and jointly predict unethical behaviour.
2. Age, gender and experience will significant moderate the relationship between career growth and unethical behaviour among customs officers.

Method

Design

The researcher adopted a cross sectional research design.

Participants

The study was carried out in Zone C of the Nigeria Customs service (NCS) which covers Abia/ Imo, Anambra/ Enugu/ Ebonyi, Ph I, Onne, Edo /Delta, Cross River /Epz/ Akwa Ibom. The Zone have a staff strength of 3,000 officers and men. Two hundred and fifty personnel were selected

through stratified sampling technique. The demographic characteristics revealed a mean age of 32.14 (S.D= 3.14) years . 64.4% of the respondents were males while 35.6% were females. Larger percentage of the respondents 71.2% were married. The educational qualification of the officers include SSCE certificate (5.6%), OND (19.6%), NCE certificate (5.6%), HND (18.4%) possess, university degree (24.8%) and master degree (3.2%). 13.6% of the respondents were inspector of customs, 18.0% were customs assistant, 4.4% were superintendent of customs, 15.2% were Assistant Superintendent of Customs – I (ASC-I) , 14.8% were in Assistant Superintendent of Customs-II (ASC-II), 9.2% were in Assistant Inspector of Customs (AIC), 4.8% were Assistant Controller (AC), 12.0% were Deputy Superintendent of Customs (DSC), 3.6% were Customs Assistant II, 2.0% were chief superintendent customs ranks while 2.4% senior officer. Larger percentage (83.2%) of the respondents were in operations, 3.2% were in transport and logistics department, 4.8% were in general duty, 2.8% were support staff department, 3.6% were in enforcement unit department while 2.4% were in management. 43.6% of the respondents have experienced it for 2-10 years, 15.2% have experienced it for 11-20 years, 28.0% have experienced it for 21-30 years while 13.2% have experienced it for 31 years and above.

Instrument

The measure contained a questionnaire pack with demographic data of participants (age, marital status, rank, number of children, educational status, religion etc), Career Growth Scale (CGS; Weng & Xi, 2010), Career Salience Scale (CSS; Allen & Orlepp, 2000) and Workplace Deviant Behaviour Scale (Bennett & Robinson, 2000). The details are explained thus:

Career Growth Scale (CGS)

CGS is a 15-item made up of four dimensions, namely; career goal progress, professional ability development, promotion speed, and remuneration growth. Higher scores indicate higher level of career growth. Respondent express their degree of agreement or disagreement on a 5-point likert-type scale ranging from very strongly disagree (score 1) to very strongly agree (score 5), and reliability coefficient for this scale was 0.86 alpha. This scale was scored by combing all the items into a single total score, computing the average score. Respondents with scores above the mean indicate high scores and being high on career growth while scores below the mean score indicates low scores and being low on career growth.

Work Salience Questionnaire (WSQ) and Career Salience Questionnaire (CSQ)

Career salience was assessed using Work Salience Questionnaire (WSQ) and Career Salience Questionnaire (CSQ) of Allen and Ortlepp (2000) were used to assess work salience and career salience respectively. Recent research found support for the scales' face, content, convergent and divergent validity, as well as internal reliability of 0.83 for the CSQ and 0.80 for the WSQ (Allen & Ortlepp, 2000). Convergent validity of the scales was established using Greenhaus' (1971) Career Salience Scale. Correlations ranged from 0.66 to 0.84 for the CSQ and between 0.26 and 0.55 for the WSQ responses was on a five -point Likert-type scale (1=Strongly Disagree; 5= Strongly Agree). The higher the score, the higher the levels of business ethics orientation, the reliability coefficient for this scale was 0.78. This scale was scored by combing all the items into a single total score index and computing the mean score. Respondents with scores above the mean indicate high scores and being high on career salience while scores below the mean score indicates low scores and being low on career salience.

Workplace Deviant Behaviour (WDB)

Unethical behaviour of Customs officers was measured using items adapted from Bennett and Robinson's (2000) Workplace Deviant Behaviour scale. This scale is made up of between deviant behaviour directed against the organization (WDBO: 10 items) and that against individuals at work (WDBI: 7 items). Responses to these items were made on a 5-point scale (1= Never, 5=Always). The coefficient alphas for the WDBO and WDBI scales used in this study were 0.82 and 0.86, respectively. Sample items from the WDBO scale include 'Intentionally work slower than you could have worked' and 'Come in late to work without permission.' Sample items from the WDBI scale include 'Act rudely toward someone at work' and 'Make fun of someone at work.'

Procedure

The researcher first sought for permission from the commander of the unit to carry out the study. After the permission was granted, the purposive sampling technique was used to sample the respondents at their various duty posts. The researcher went about administering questionnaires personally to the officers of the unit at their various duty shields. The researchers explained to the respondents that the questionnaire is strictly for research purpose. The respondents were assured that the information would be treated confidentially. The researchers ensure that the no personal identifier (for example name or service number) was included in the questionnaire. Verbal consent was obtained from the officers and men before the questionnaire was administered on the participants. Only officers and men who agreed to the informed consent participated in the study. The respondents were selected using purposive sampling technique. A maximum of one week duration was allotted to the data collection. Two hundred and eighty questionnaires were distributed but only two hundred and fifty questionnaires were retrieved. Only the questionnaires that were well filled were analysed in the study.

Statistical Analysis

Having gathered the data from the field, the researcher entered the data using the data into the computer using SPSS. After the data entry process, the data was analysed using both descriptive and inferential statistics. The collected data was analyzed using the SPSS 20.0 software. The statistical tests to be use include t- test for independent samples to test hypotheses 1-2 at 0.05 level of significance. This study involved analyzing the ability of socio-demographic variables (as indicated by the age, gender) and career factors (career salience and career growth) to predict unethical work behaviour, and career growth role as a moderator. As a result, moderation effects were tested, using multiple regression analysis, as suggested by Baron and Kenny (1986). Multiple regression analysis as described by Baron and Kenny (1986) is the most widely used method to assess moderation (MacKinnon & MacKinnon, 2008).Furthermore, statistical analysis procedures conducted in SPSS

Results

Correlation analysis

Before regression analyses were initiated, Pearson correlations were calculated to test if any demographic variables (i.e., age, gender), career related variables and outcome variables (unethical work behaviour) of the moderation analysis.

Table 1: Pearson and Point-biserial correlations for independent, moderator and the dependent variables

Variables	M	SD	1	2	3	4	5	6
1. Unethical behaviour	47.90	20.46	-	.003	.277**	.251**	-.434**	.244**
2. Age	40.25	9.57		-	-.253**	.742**	.066	.226**
3. Sex	1.36	.47			-	-.096	-.129*	-.078
4. Years of experience	18.50	10.01				-	.038	.152*
5. Career growth	49.08	12.71					-	.001
6. Career salience	35.56	11.22						-

** . Correlation is significant at the 0.01 level (2-tailed).

* . Correlation is significant at the 0.05 level (2-tailed).

Table 1 reports the descriptive statistics and bivariate correlations for the study variables. Career growth had an inverse association with unethical work behaviour ($r = -.43, p < .001$); Also, there were positive associations between career salience and unethical work behaviour ($r = .24, p < .001$), gender and unethical work behaviour ($r_{pb} = .28, p < .001$), and years of experience and unethical work behaviour ($r = .25, p < .001$).

Hypotheses

1 Career salience, career growth and socio-demographic variables would significantly and jointly predict unethical behaviour.

Multiple regression analysis was conducted and the summary of results presented in Table 2:

Table 2: Summary of multiple Regression Analysis for Variables Predicting unethical behaviour among customs officers (N = 250)

	B	S.E	β	t	Sig.	95.0% Confidence Interval LO- HI	R	R ²	df	F	Sig.
(Constant)	62.21	7.93		7.85	.000	46.59 77.81	.65	.42	5,244	35.79	.000
Age	-.76	.16	-.36	-4.66	.000	-1.08 -.44					
Sex	8.74	2.18	.21	4.01	.000	4.45 13.04					
Years of experience	1.04	.15	.51	6.95	.000	.747 1.34					
Career growth	-.65	.08	-.40	-8.23	.000	-.805 -.49					
Career salience	.48	.09	.26	5.28	.000	.302 .66					

Dependent Variable: Unethical behavior

Results indicated that career salience ($\beta = -.40, p < .01$), and career growth ($\beta = .26, p < .01$), were significantly related to exhibition of unethical behaviour in the workplace ($\beta = .22, p < .01$), after

controlling for age ($\beta = -.36, p < .01$), gender ($\beta = .21, p < .01$), and experience ($\beta = .51, p < .01$) which were significant ;thus, supporting Hypothesis 1.

Hypothesis II

H₂: Age, gender and experience will significant moderate the relationship between career growth and unethical behaviour among customs officers.

Moderation was examined using hierarchical multiple regression analysis, following procedures outlined by Field (2009). The regression model was utilized to assess the potential effect of career growth on the ability of psycho-social predictors to predict unethical work behaviour, the dependent or outcome variable. Variables deemed necessary to include as covariates, Sex and age, were entered into Step 1 of the regression model as control variables. For Step 2, the career salience and career growth score was entered. For Step 3, an interaction term for sex, age and career salience by career growth, created by multiplying these variables, was entered.

Table 3: Summary of moderated Hierarchical Regression Analysis for Variables Predicting unethical behaviour among customs officers (N = 250)

	B	S.E	β	t	Sig.	95.0% Confidence Interval		B	S.E	β	Sig.	95.0% Confidence Interval		B	S.E	β	Sig.	95.0% Confidence Interval			
						LO-HI	LO-HI					LO-HI	LO-HI								
(Constant)	40.96	7.51		5.45	.00	26.17	55.76	62.20	7.93		7.85	.00	46.59	77.81	51.79	7.99		6.49	.00	36.07	7.52
Age	-.66	.19	-.31	-3.45	.00	-1.03	-.28	-.76	.16	-.36	-4.66	.00	-1.08	-.44	-.70	.16	-.33	-4.50	.00	-1.01	-.40
Sex	10.58	2.55	.25	4.15	.00	5.55	15.60	8.74	2.18	.20	4.01	.00	4.45	13.04	9.70	2.10	.23	4.63	.00	5.57	13.83
Years of experience	1.03	.18	.50	5.81	.00	.68	1.37	1.04	.15	.51	6.95	.00	.75	1.34	1.09	.14	.53	7.60	.00	.81	1.37
Career growth								-.65	.08	-.40	-8.23	.00	-.81	-.49	-.53	.08	-.33	-6.71	.00	-.68	-.37
Career salience								.48	.09	.26	5.28	.00	.30	.66	.47	.10	.26	4.84	.00	.28	.66
CG X Career Salience														-.04	1.23	.00	-.04	.97	-2.48	2.39	
CG X Sex														-5.14	1.05	-.27	-4.89	.00	-7.21	-3.07	
CG X Age														-4.42	1.09	-.22	-4.06	.00	-6.56	-2.27	
R		.44**							.65*						.695						
R Square		.194**							.423						.483						
R Square Change		.194**							.23*						.06*						
F		19.68*							35.7						28.1						
F Change		19.68*							48.5						9.34						

a. Dependent Variable: Unethical behaviour

In the moderated hierarchical regression analysis, the first step (model 1), assess the contribution of socio-demographic characteristics (age, gender, and years of experience); the control variables as predictors of unethical behaviour. The results indicated that the first model was significant ($F_{(3, 247)} = 19.68, p < .01; R^2 = .194$). This model explained 19.4% of the proportion of the variance observed in unethical work behaviour. As shown age ($\beta = -.31, p = .000$), sex ($\beta = .25, p = .001$), and experience ($\beta = .50, p = 0.000$) predicted unethical work behaviour among the customs officers and men (see Table 3).

In the second step (model 2), career factors were entered as the independent variables. A significant fit was also recorded in the second model. The addition of career growth and salience significantly increased the fit of the model ($F_{(5, 245)} = 35.79, p = .000, R^2 = 0.423, \Delta R^2 = 0.23$), accounting for a significant proportion of additional variance in unethical work behaviour scores, $\Delta R^2 = .23, \Delta F(1, 245) = 48.55, p = .001$. In this model, career growth ($\beta = -0.65, p = .000$), and career salience ($\beta = 0.48, p = .000$) were significantly associated with unethical behaviour reported by Customs officers and men (see Table 3).

The third and final step (model 3) involved including the interaction between age, sex, and years of experience with career growth for predicting unethical behaviour among NCS personnel. These addition significantly increased the fit of the model ($F_{(8, 252)} = 28.17, p = .003, R^2 = 0.48, \Delta R^2 = 0.06$). addition of the interaction terms added significant 6% additional variance, $\Delta R^2 = .06, \Delta F(1, 242) = 9.34, p = .003$ to the model. The interaction terms of Career growth x Sex ($\beta = -.27, p < .01$) and that of Career growth x Age ($\beta = -.22, p < .01$) were significant; however, the interaction of career growth with years of experience was not significant (see Table 3). For better illustration interaction graphs was plotted to illustrate the interaction between career growth, age and sex. A mean split was used to classify career growth in to poor and good career growth.

Fig 1 shows that career growth has significant influence on unethical behaviour. Female customs personnel with poor growth had the higher unethical behaviour than female officers with good

career growth and dyads of male officers with poor or good career growth. These shows that unethical behaviour more magnified for females who experience poor career growth compared to males of poor career growth.

Fig 2 shows that age -related effect career growth is magnified for those that are younger between age 22 – 30 years and those that are 40 years and above. The interaction graphs demonstrated a curvilinear relationship Thus, the second hypothesis is thus supported.

Discussion

This study investigated the moderating influence of age, gender and experience on the relationship of career growth, career salience with customs officers’ unethical behaviour. The hypothesis stated that career salience, career growth and socio-demographic variables would significantly and jointly predict unethical behaviour.was confirmed. Customs officers with poor growth reported more unethical behaviour than officer with good career growth who reported lesser unethical behaviour. The findings is in line with the findings of Boes (2010) who demonstrated that being a lower level employees without adequate long term goals pressures employees to act unethically. Employees with long term goals such as career advancement tend to behave more ethically than employees with short term goals in the organisations. This finding agrees with the study of Trevinor and Brown (2005) who identified that top flying leaders in organisations are socially salient in their career and organizations thus the prominence of their career role.

However contrary to expectation a positive association was observed between career salience and unethical behaviour. This is in contrast to the believe that people who view work as

a merely keeping a job, rather than seeing it as a calling associated with a higher purpose, are more likely to be ensnared by the allure of the material rewards they receive from work, hence they might be more likely to sacrificing their career for material gains than psychological benefits that they receive from the organisation (Parry 2006; Van Zyl et al 2010). This is findings is not farfetched as career stagnation often lead to changes in career beliefs.

The moderating effect of age and gender were significant this is consistent with findings which have shown that gender differences (sex) was demonstrated to influence the relationship between career growth and unethical behaviour. the findings justified that that female employees often react less strongly to distributive justice than male employees (Khoreva & Tenhiälä, 2016). While it established following the trajectory of studies which demonstrated that female employees have been found to react more strongly to procedural justice than their male counterparts (Clay-Warner, Culatta & James, 2013), It is evident that females react more to procedural(un)fairness than men, even if they do not always show it via expressed or noticed behavioural differences (Dulebohn et al., 2016). This is expected as the women face multiple sources for factors which limit their career growth such as the glass-ceiling phenomenon and work-family conflict factors. As such women tend to stagnate more in their career growth compared to the males thus become more sensitive to unfairness and injustice compare to the males. Women tend to be more emotional when reacting to procedural injustice and the problems of double jeopardy having to face more underlining problems in getting promotions than men.

The study demonstrated a negative relationship between employee age and unethical behaviour. These findings support the norm found in prior studies were negative associations was found for age association with antisocial tendencies such as deviance, and related constructs such as revenge and retaliation (Bobocel, 2013). Age have been demonstrated to influence the perception of organizational justice and the subsequent reaction such as deviance and unethical work behaviour (Bobocel, 2013; Kooij et al., 2011; Khoreva & Tenhiälä, 2016). In comparison to younger employees, the conclusion that levels of deviation from the workplace are lower in the medium-term and older workers can be explained in two ways. First, the elderly and the middle-aged respondents may differ considerably from the younger respondents. Individuals who share a temporary experience, such as a similar year of birth, could be compared with others born in a later period of time and act differently at work (i.e., cohort effect). Secondly, and most probably, changes in individuals as they age, develop and mature might explain the findings. We argue that changes in the personality and emotions of adults over their lifetime may explain these disparities in age-related variances in ethical work conduct.

Conclusion and Recommendations

This study examined the psycho-social factors influencing the unethical work behaviour among Customs officers in Edo-delta command Nigeria. This study thus concluded that age and gender differences moderated the relationship between career growth and unethical behaviour at work. Customs officers who experience consistent career growth were found to be less involved in unethical compared to those who experienced poor career growth. Females and younger personnel with poor career growth tend to be more unethical behaviours. This study recommends that:

1. The customs authorities should look into ways of improving the working condition of the customs officers especially in the area of personnel development.
2. As the career has high worth for the job holders, employers should provide their employees with a comfortable working environment along with flexible working hours

so that they feel satisfied with their working environment leading to low involvement in deviant behaviours.

3. Employers should be equal in giving compensations and benefits to employees as per to their efforts and the working environment should be justified so that injustice perceptions don't initiate deviant behaviour in employees.

Limitation of study and recommendation for future studies

One of the limitations of this study is that it is cross-sectional in strategy. Secondly, data collection was affected due to the difficulty of maintaining contact with the respondents for a long period of time. Also, the study is limited to a single formation in the customs formation in the Nigerian customs, thus the generalisation of the research findings to the whole the customs service may be limited due to its level of its sophistication and differences in policy as regards different units and formations. The study focused on perception of pay and educational qualification. In the future, it is suggested that the key constructs which include and job motivations and pay equity should be further explored and compared across other occupational groups within the Nigerian customs.

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